

Paper 5

STUDY ON MILLENNIAL PERCEPTION ON MARKETING INNOVATION

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Abstract:

This paper deals with the study on the impact of Digital Marketing towards Millennial people who born age between 1981 to 1999. The objective of the study is to analyse how Millennial Use Digital Media, how much and the reason for using digital media. The paper gives about the role of youths in the Digital Industry. It basically explains how important is digital Marketing and helps it's changing the company's marketing strategies. The reason for conducting this study is to observe various marketing strategies that are used in Digital Media and determine which ones are preferred by Millennial and are effective in influencing their perception and behaviour. This study has 104 Millennial responses are used on Digital Media daily in their life, more importantly, this study highlights millennial view web site frequently write online product review that people will see Digital Ads rarely for Millennial do not like pop up ads and they like Visuals in websites and actual grabbing attention of products or services.

Keywords: Digital marketing: Internet, Digital media, millennial, Digital industry, Perception.

1. INTRODUCTION

Digital Marketing or E-Marketing refers to the use of marketing techniques through Digital Media or Internet like social media, websites, blogs etc. With increasing usage of digital marketing consumers and companies can able to reach their targets easily. It is all about the targeted, measurable, and interactive marketing of end products or services with the use of digital technologies and media to reach and transfer leads into clients and retain them[1]. Millennial has been identified as a driving force behaving digital media and online shopping. Millennial or Gen Y people's unusual attraction both Academic and Managers works. Gen Y people are called as first-generation people who use Digital Media or Internet for the purpose of getting information or to buy products[2].

2 STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Study on Millennial Perception and Behaviour regarding Digital Marketing/Digital Media with special reference to Stream LL Bengaluru”.

3 NEED FOR THE STUDY

Using digital advertising and marketing or net advertising and marketing is very crucial for any enterprise. These youths will affect deeply on the market because of the regular use of Digital Medias.[3]

4 LITERATURE REVIEW

J Järvinen, H Karjaluoto - Industrial Marketing Management, (2015). This study explains the performance of the companies by using Web analytics. The main purpose of this study to measure literature and use web analytics. This offers companies to measure Digital Marketing performance. The study shows that organizations efforts to use marketing metrics system and the resulting outcome cannot be understood without seeing the processing of metrics data and use of the system. should update their capabilities and also use current or modern Digital Marketing Techniques.

5 OBJECTIVES & METHODOLOGY

To Analyse the Millennial Perception towards Digital Marketing to know their view about digital media, online marketing, online shopping, and promotional activity with Digital Marketing[4][8] To Analyse the Millennial Behaviour towards Digital Marketing, Digital Media, online shopping and ads. For this study methodology adopted the data interview of primary data gathering. The source of secondary data collection is from books, websites, and journals

6. ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Figure No. 1.1 Response on Role of Website Design

Role of Website Design in Digital Marketing	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Disagree	2	2
Moderate Disagree	8	8
No opinion	27	26
Moderate agree	24	23
Agree	43	41
Total	104	100

Table no 1.1 clearly state that Majority that is 41% of respondents agree to this statement

Figure No. 1.2 Responses regarding knowledge of Digital Marketing

Knowledge regarding Digital Marketing	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Yes	103	99
No	1	1
Total	104	100

Table no.1.2 clearly state that 99% of respondents are having knowledge about Digital Marketing.

Figure No. 1.3 Response regarding interest in learning Digital Marketing

Regarding interest in learning Digital Marketing	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Yes	8	9
Maybe in Future	59	57
Already know about the concepts	5	5
Not Interested	31	29
Total	104	100

Table no 1.3 this clearly state that 9% of respondents have interest, 57% of respondents thought to learn in future, 5% of respondents already know about Digital Marketing, 29% of respondents no interest in learning digital marketing

Table No. 1.4 Response regarding information is needed before joining any Digital Marketingcourse

Information about Digital Marketing course	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Strongly agree	55	52
Agree	39	37
Disagree	1	1
Strong disagree	10	10
Total	104	100

Table No. 1.4 clearly state majority that is 52% of respondents strongly agree to this statement, 37% of respondents agree with the statement, 10% of respondents strongly disagree to the statement, 1% of respondent disagree to the statement

Figure No. 1.5 Response regarding the familiarity with Digital Marketing Techniques

Digital Marketing Techniques	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
SEO	3	3
SEM	5	5
Social Media marketing	66	62
E-mail Marketing	11	11
Pay-per-click advertising (PPC)	3	3

Content marketing	3	3
All the above	5	5
None of above	8	8
Total	104	100

Table no 1.5 reveals that majority that is 62% of respondents are familiar with Social Media Marketing

7. FINDINGS

- Majority of the respondents believe that by using web site design it is easy to get information about the products.
- Majority of the respondents agree that Digital Marketing is going to replace Traditional Marketing.
- The study clearly shows that all the respondents heard about Digital Marketing.
- By analysing the above study most of the respondents heard about Digital Marketing through social media
- 59% of the respondents were interested to learn digital marketing in future and 9% were really interested to learn immediately
- From the above study majority of the respondents agree that they need much information about Digital Marketing.
- By analysing data from the study majority of the respondents agree that, there is great Job opportunity for Millennial to Digital Marketing Industry.
- Majority of the respondents moderately agree that choice of Digital Marketing is best for the future job option.

8. SUGGESTIONS

- Web site design is the main attraction in Digital Marketing but most the people pay less attention to that so more attention in website design has to be done.
- Strategic Promotion of Digital Marketing is the need of the day.
- Good website for Digital Marketing with information regarding the concepts and techniques and online course, queries etc.
- More and more pop up ads will disturb to viewers.
- By providing online course facility people may come to learn Digital Marketing.
- Encouraging Millennial to study digital marketing is the need of the day

9. CONCLUSION

In future India with the use of digital marketing has tremendous growth in the national income and it helps many start-ups to grow their business in a big way. The internet penetration rate in India has increased to the greatest extent. And also the small or medium level business can get a very good benefit from the Digital Marketing [6]. Usage of internet by maximum number of people in the country would help in the development of the business in the country and there will be more demand for the domestic products as well [5]. Since all most all young and adults of the world are having connection with web it would be very easy for the marketers to target the customers making it cost effective, as traditional marketing is taken over Digital marketing.

importance should be given to the growth of digital marketing concentrating on Millennial by analysing their perception and expectation as they can be involved in making digital marketing much more effective therefore, Younger generation should be encouraged to take up digital marketing as a job opportunity and create awareness among them is the need of the day[11,12].

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